

Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support for the Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program at St. Paul University Philippines

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Abstract

This study aimed to design, develop, and evaluate a web-based Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support for the Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program at St. Paul University Philippines. The project was undertaken in response to the identified challenges in the existing manual process, which relied on word processing software for storing applicant information and generating reports. The manual system posed risks of inefficiency, data inaccuracy, and delayed decision-making. Using the Agile Scrum Methodology, the system was iteratively developed to automate application tracking, provide real-time status monitoring, and deliver decision support tools. Four key features were integrated into the system: the Priority Alerts and Reminders Dashboard, Application Status Overview, Comparative Reporting Tools, and Applicant Profile Summaries. System evaluation based on the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards showed that the system achieved a very great extent of compliance across all eight quality characteristics, including functional suitability, performance efficiency, usability, and security. Additionally, user acceptance was measured using the Technology Acceptance Model, with results showing strong agreement on the system's ease of use, usefulness, intention to use, and overall satisfaction. The findings confirm that the system successfully addressed the existing challenges by improving data management, process efficiency, and decision-making for ETEEAP applications. The system offers a sustainable digital solution that enhances administrative operations and user experience, positioning it as a practical tool for institutional adoption. Recommendations for future enhancements include adding document upload features, role-based access control, and expanded reporting options.

Keywords: *Applicant Tracking System, Decision Support System, ISO/IEC 25010, Technology Acceptance Model, Agile Scrum Methodology, System Evaluation, User Acceptance.*

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Introduction

In the era of digital transformation, higher education institutions worldwide are increasingly adopting technology-driven solutions to streamline administrative and academic processes. Among these solutions, Applicant Tracking and Management Systems have become critical tools in managing large volumes of

student applications efficiently. These systems support institutions in automating the collection, evaluation, and reporting of applicant information, thereby improving decision-making processes and service delivery (Benavides et al., 2020). Globally, universities and accreditation bodies utilize these systems to ensure accurate data handling, minimize human error, and reduce the administrative burden associated with traditional, manual methods.

In the Philippines, where access to higher education is expanding through government-recognized programs such as the Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program (ETEEAP), the need for efficient applicant tracking systems becomes even more significant. The ETEEAP, authorized by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), allows working professionals to earn academic degrees by recognizing their prior learning and work experiences (CHED Memorandum Order No. 36, Series of 1997). As more professionals seek to enhance their qualifications through this program, higher education institutions face challenges in managing growing application data, maintaining records, and generating reports for regulatory and administrative purposes. However, many institutions continue to rely on outdated tools such as spreadsheets or word processing software, which pose risks of data inconsistency, inefficiency, and reporting inaccuracies (Lapitan et al., 2021).

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Recognizing the strategic importance of the ETEEAP in providing educational opportunities to working professionals and strengthening the university's community engagement, the researchers were inspired to address these limitations by developing a specialized system. This system aims to provide real-time tracking, structured applicant profiles, automated status monitoring, and decision support features that will assist administrators in streamlining their processes, improving data accuracy, and facilitating better reporting. By doing so, the proposed system will not only improve administrative efficiency but also support SPUP's mission to provide accessible, quality education aligned with national and global standards.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to design and develop an Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support to assist St. Paul University Philippines in effectively managing the application process for the Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program, providing real-time application monitoring, structured applicant profiling, and decision support tools for improved administrative processing and reporting.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the existing problems and challenges encountered by the SPUP International Relations Office in tracking and managing ETEEAP applications?
2. What system can be developed to address the identified problems and challenges?
3. To what extent does the developed system comply with the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards in terms of: (3.1. Functional Suitability; 3.2. Performance Efficiency; 3.3. Compatibility; 3.4. Usability; 3.5. Reliability; 3.6. Security; 3.7. Maintainability; 3.8. Portability)

4. To what extent do the stakeholders accept the developed system based on the Technology Acceptance Model in terms of: (4.1. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU); 4.2. Perceived Usefulness (PU); 4.3. Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU); 4.4. Overall System Satisfaction (OSS))

5. What enhancements can be done to improve the functionality and effectiveness of the developed system?

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

This study adopts the Input-Process-Output-Outcome (IPOO) model because it provides a clear and structured way of showing how the system will be designed, developed, evaluated, and used. It helps explain how the different elements of the study work together to solve the identified problems in managing ETEEAP applications. The inputs of the study include the problems and challenges in tracking and managing ETEEAP applications, the applicant data such as personal information, education, and work experience, the existing practices and tools currently used by SPUP such as manual word processing files, the CHED Memorandum Order No. 36, s. 1997, the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards, and the Technology Acceptance Model to assess user acceptance. The process involves developing the system using the Agile Scrum Methodology through continuous feedback and testing. The system is evaluated based on software quality standards and user acceptance focusing on ease of use, usefulness, intention to use, and satisfaction. The output is a web-based Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support that provides real-time tracking, applicant profiling, and reporting features. The outcome is improved management of ETEEAP applications, better decision-making, and higher user satisfaction. The significance of this framework lies in its ability to guide the study in a clear and practical way, making sure that the system addresses real problems, meets quality standards, and is acceptable and easy to use for both administrators and applicants. This ensures that the system becomes a useful tool for improving the delivery of the ETEEAP program at SPUP.

Methodologies

This study employed a descriptive-developmental research design to guide the design, development, and evaluation of an Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support. The descriptive phase involved identifying the current practices, challenges, and limitations in managing ETEEAP applications, which are currently done through manual methods using word processing software. The

developmental phase focused on creating a digital solution to address these challenges by designing, building, and testing a web-based system that would streamline application tracking, profiling, and reporting.

Figure 2. Scrum Methodology. Adapted from “11 Project Management Techniques to Choose From,” by SoftwareSuggest, n.d., SoftwareSuggest

Source: <https://www.softwaresuggest.com/blog/project-management-techniques/>

To organize the system development process, the Agile Scrum Methodology was used. This approach allowed the proponent to develop the system iteratively through sprint cycles, enabling continuous testing, user feedback, and refinements across multiple modules of the platform. Each sprint consisted of planning, daily scrums, execution, reviews, and retrospective evaluations, ensuring that the system evolved based on real-time user input and observations (see Figure 2).

The participants of the study included the Director of the International Relations Office, who oversees the ETEEAP program; Registrar’s Office staff, who are responsible for assigning subjects to qualified applicants; Business Affairs Office staff, who assess the fees of the applicants; and the ETEEAP applicants (students) themselves, who will use the system to apply and track their application status. Additionally, ten (10) IT experts were engaged to evaluate the system in terms of its technical quality, usability, and overall performance.

The system was evaluated based on the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards, which cover eight key characteristics: Functional Suitability, Performance Efficiency, Compatibility, Usability, Reliability, Security, Maintainability, and Portability. Data were collected through system walkthroughs, user observations, and standardized evaluation forms. A 5-point Likert scale was used to quantify expert evaluations, with 1 representing “Very Poor” and 5 representing “Very Good.” The results were analyzed using descriptive statistics, specifically mean scores and standard deviation, to determine the level of compliance with the ISO/IEC 25010 standards. Qualitative feedback was also gathered to identify the system’s strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

In addition to quality evaluation, the system’s user acceptance was assessed using the Technology Acceptance Model. This assessment focused on four key areas: Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU), Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU), and Overall System Satisfaction (OSS). The same 5-point Likert scale was used to interpret user responses, where 4.20 to 5.00 indicated “Strongly Agree,” 3.40 to 4.19 indicated “Agree,” 2.60 to 3.39 indicated “Neutral,” 1.80 to 2.59 indicated “Disagree,” and

1.00 to 1.79 indicated “Strongly Disagree.” The results from this assessment provided insights into how the system was received by its intended users, both from the administrative side and from the applicants’ perspective.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study. All participants provided informed consent before their participation, and the privacy and confidentiality of the data collected, especially applicant information, were safeguarded throughout the development and testing phases. All collected data were used solely for the purpose of improving the system and ensuring its effectiveness in supporting the delivery of the ETEEAP program at St. Paul University Philippines.

Results and Discussions

Existing Problems and Challenges Encountered by the SPUP International Relations Office in Tracking and Managing ETEEAP Applications

Through interviews, system walkthroughs, and direct observation of current practices, the study identified several existing problems and challenges encountered by the SPUP International Relations Office in managing the ETEEAP application process. First, the office currently relies on manual record-keeping using word processing software to store applicant information such as personal data, educational background, work experience, and learning objectives. This method lacks a centralized database, making it difficult to retrieve, organize, and update applicant records efficiently. The absence of automated tools also means that the office spends a significant amount of time manually reviewing files and compiling reports. Second, the process of monitoring application status is prone to inconsistencies. Since records are kept in multiple files or folders, it is challenging for the administrators to track the real-time status of each application, whether pending, approved, or rejected. This increases the risk of overlooking applications, resulting in processing delays and missed deadlines. Third, the generation of statistical reports on the number of applicants, their statuses, and other relevant data is tedious and error-prone. Reports must be manually prepared, which not only consumes time but also increases the likelihood of incorrect data being reported due to human error. Fourth, applicants do not have a way to check their application status in real time. They often have to contact the office via email, phone, or in person to inquire about their application progress. This increases the workload on administrative staff and contributes to longer response times for applicants seeking updates.

Finally, the current system lacks decision support tools that would allow the office to quickly view summaries, prioritize pending applications, or analyze trends in applications over time. Without these tools, administrative decisions are made based on manually gathered information, limiting the office's ability to respond proactively to workload demands or program performance insights. These identified challenges highlight the need for an automated Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support that can centralize data, streamline workflows, generate real-time reports, and provide applicants and administrators with a more efficient, accurate, and user-friendly experience.

The Development of the Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support for ETEEAP

In response to the challenges identified in the manual tracking and management of ETEEAP applications at St. Paul University Philippines, an Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support was designed and developed. The system was built as a web-based platform to provide real-time, centralized management of ETEEAP applicants, addressing the inefficiencies and limitations of the existing manual process. It was developed using the Agile Scrum methodology, which allowed for iterative improvements based on user feedback and system evaluations. One of the key features integrated into the system is the Priority Alerts and Reminders Dashboard. This feature provides administrators with real-time notifications of pending applications that are nearing or have passed their processing deadlines. Applications that are approaching their deadline are color-coded in yellow, while overdue

applications are highlighted in red, making it easier for administrators to prioritize their workload. To further support timely processing, the system is equipped with automated email notifications that alert staff about applications requiring immediate attention, reducing the risk of overlooked or delayed submissions.

The system also includes an Application Status Overview, which presents administrators with real-time counters showing the total number of applications, as well as the number of applications that are pending, approved, or rejected. This summary is displayed on the dashboard, providing a quick snapshot of the overall application status. Additionally, the system features graphical views in the form of pie charts and bar charts, which help visualize the distribution of application statuses, allowing administrators to easily monitor the progress of the ETEEAP program. Another important decision support feature is the Comparative Reporting Tools. These tools allow administrators to generate visual reports that present application outcomes over monthly, quarterly, and annual periods. Using bar charts and pie charts, the system helps identify patterns and trends in application submissions, approvals, and rejections over time. This feature provides valuable insights that can be used for administrative planning, resource allocation, and program evaluation, supporting data-driven decision-making processes.

Lastly, the system includes Applicant Profile Summaries, which present a structured, one-page view of each applicant’s information. These summaries include key details such as personal information, educational background, work experience, honors and awards, creative works, and lifelong learning activities. This feature makes it easier for administrators to review applicant qualifications during the evaluation and approval process, ensuring that all necessary information is readily accessible and organized in a user-friendly format. By integrating these four decision support features, the developed system not only automates the management of ETEEAP applications but also empowers the International Relations Office with tools to prioritize tasks, monitor program performance, generate meaningful reports, and facilitate informed decision-making. This development marks a significant improvement over the previous manual process, supporting SPUP’s goal of providing a more efficient, accurate, and responsive ETEEAP application management experience.

Extent of Compliance of the Developed System with the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Compliance of the Developed System with the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standard

ISO/IEC 25010 Characteristics Criteria	Category Mean	Descriptive Rating
A. Functional Suitability	4.50	Very Great Extent
B. Performance Efficiency	4.30	Very Great Extent
C. Compatibility	4.55	Very Great Extent
D. Usability	4.35	Very Great Extent
E. Reliability	4.33	Very Great Extent
F. Security	4.62	Very Great Extent
G. Maintainability	4.34	Very Great Extent
H. Portability	4.73	Very Great Extent
Category Mean	4.46	Very Great Extent

The developed Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support for ETEEAP was evaluated based on the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards, covering eight key software quality characteristics. The evaluation was conducted by ten IT experts using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 indicated “Very Poor” and 5 indicated “Very Good.” The results showed that the system achieved a category mean of 4.46, interpreted as a very great extent of compliance with the standards.

In terms of Functional Suitability, the system received a mean rating of 4.50, indicating that it effectively fulfills its intended functions and meets user requirements. This finding is consistent with the study of Sarwosri et al. (2023), who emphasized the importance of functional suitability in improving academic information systems. The system also demonstrated strong Performance Efficiency, receiving a mean rating of 4.30, showing that it performs efficiently in terms of response time and resource usage. According to Yenduri and Gadekallu (2022), performance efficiency plays a crucial role in ensuring software maintainability and user satisfaction.

For Compatibility, the system achieved a mean rating of 4.55, proving that it can integrate well with other platforms and devices. This is aligned with the ISO/IEC 25010 standards, which highlight the importance of compatibility in achieving seamless system interoperability (ISO, 2011). The Usability of the system was also highly rated, with a mean score of 4.35, reflecting that users found the system easy to learn and operate, which is essential for encouraging adoption and satisfaction. The ISO/IEC 25010 model identifies usability as a key determinant of software quality and user acceptance (ISO, 2011).

In terms of Reliability, the system scored 4.33, demonstrating consistent performance without system failures. This meets the standard's requirement for reliable operations in mission-critical systems (ISO, 2011). The Security of the system was rated the highest among all characteristics, with a mean score of 4.62, ensuring that data is protected and unauthorized access is prevented. This reflects the ISO/IEC 25010's emphasis on security as a fundamental quality requirement (ISO, 2011).

The Maintainability of the system, with a mean rating of 4.34, indicates that it is designed for easy updates and modifications, ensuring that it can adapt to future needs without requiring major rework. Finally, the system's Portability received the highest mean score of 4.73, showing that the system can be deployed in different environments with minimal effort, further supporting its flexibility and usability across platforms.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the developed system meets the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards to a very great extent, ensuring that it is functional, efficient, compatible, user-friendly, reliable, secure, maintainable, and portable. This high level of compliance confirms that the system is well-suited to support the ETEEAP processes of St. Paul University Philippines by providing a robust and reliable digital solution.

Extent of Evaluation of the Stakeholders with the Technology Acceptance Model

Table 2. Summary of Stakeholders' Evaluation of the Developed System Using the Technology Acceptance Model

ISO/IEC 25010 Characteristics	Criteria	Category Mean	Descriptive Rating
I.	A. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)	4.55	Strongly Agree
J.	B. Perceived Usefulness (PU)	4.65	Strongly Agree
K.	C. Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU)	4.68	Strongly Agree
L.	D. Overall System Satisfaction (OSS)	4.74	Strongly Agree
Category Mean		4.65	Strongly Agree

The developed Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support for ETEEAP was further evaluated by key stakeholders using the Technology Acceptance Model. The results of the TAM evaluation showed a category mean of 4.65, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," indicating a high level of acceptance and satisfaction among the users. Specifically, Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) received a mean score of 4.55, suggesting that users found the system easy to learn and navigate. This aligns with Davis's (1989) assertion that perceived ease of use significantly influences user acceptance of technology. Perceived Usefulness (PU) achieved a mean score of 4.65, reflecting users' belief that the system helps them perform their tasks more efficiently and supports their role in the ETEEAP application process.

This is consistent with findings by Venkatesh and Davis (2000), who emphasized the critical role of perceived usefulness in technology adoption.

Meanwhile, Behavioral Intention to Use (BIU) was rated 4.68, indicating that users expressed a strong willingness to continue using the system in the future. This suggests that the system meets user expectations and encourages long-term adoption. Finally, Overall System Satisfaction received the highest rating of 4.74, showing that users were highly satisfied with the system's overall functionality, design, and performance. These results confirm that the system is not only technically sound but also highly accepted by its target users. The strong ratings across all TAM dimensions indicate that the system effectively meets user needs, promotes ease of use, delivers practical benefits, and provides a satisfying experience. This level of user acceptance is crucial for ensuring that the system will be adopted and integrated into the university's operational processes for managing ETEEAP applications.

Recommendations for System Enhancement

Based on the evaluation results and qualitative feedback from IT experts and key stakeholders, several enhancements are recommended to further improve the system. First, the integration of role-based access control is suggested to allow different levels of access and permissions for administrators, staff, and applicants, thereby strengthening data privacy and security management. Second, adding a document upload and management feature would allow applicants to submit scanned copies of their supporting documents, such as diplomas, certificates, and employment records, directly through the platform, reducing the need for separate email submissions. Third, the system could benefit from an automated application verification workflow, which would allow administrators to mark applications as "For Review," "Under Evaluation," or "For Final Approval," providing a more structured review process. Fourth, incorporating a notification system for applicants, such as email or SMS alerts for application status updates, would enhance the communication process and improve user experience. Finally, adding a comprehensive reporting module that allows administrators to export reports in various formats (PDF, Excel) could further support documentation and reporting requirements for university and CHED submissions. These enhancements aim to build on the system's current strengths by improving functionality, security, user engagement, and reporting capabilities, ensuring that it continues to meet the evolving needs of SPUP's ETEEAP program.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to design, develop, and evaluate an Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support for the Expanded Tertiary Education Equivalency and Accreditation Program of St. Paul University Philippines, addressing the identified challenges in the manual management of applicant records. The results of the descriptive phase confirmed the limitations of the existing manual process, particularly in the areas of data organization, status monitoring, reporting, and decision-making support.

Through the application of the Agile Scrum Methodology, the system was successfully developed to automate and streamline the tracking and management of ETEEAP applications. Four key Decision Support Features, the Priority Alerts and Reminders Dashboard, Application Status Overview, Comparative Reporting Tools, and Applicant Profile Summaries - were integrated to enhance administrative efficiency and improve data-driven decision-making.

The system's compliance with the ISO/IEC 25010 Software Quality Standards was evaluated by IT experts and was rated to a very great extent across all eight quality characteristics, confirming the system's functional suitability, performance efficiency, compatibility, usability, reliability, security, maintainability, and portability. Additionally, the Technology Acceptance Model evaluation showed that stakeholders, including administrators and ETEEAP applicants, strongly agreed on the system's ease of use, usefulness, intention to use, and overall satisfaction.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the developed system effectively addresses the challenges faced by the SPUP International Relations Office in managing ETEEAP applications. The system not only improves administrative workflows but also provides users with a reliable, secure, and user-friendly platform for application tracking and management. The high levels of quality compliance and user acceptance demonstrate the system's potential to be fully adopted and sustained as part of SPUP's operational processes in delivering the ETEEAP program.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, conclusions, and system evaluation results, the following recommendations are presented to further improve the delivery, adoption, and future development of the Applicant Tracking and Management System with Decision Support for ETEEAP at St. Paul University Philippines:

1. It is recommended that the university officially adopt and institutionalize the developed system as the standard platform for managing ETEEAP applications. Adequate resources should be allocated for its continuous maintenance, server hosting, data security, and user training to ensure the system's long-term sustainability and integration into the university's digital services.
2. The Office of International Relations is encouraged to fully transition from manual processing to the developed system to streamline operations, reduce administrative workload, and improve the accuracy of reports and applicant monitoring. Regular usage and feedback collection from office staff are also recommended to support continuous system improvement.
3. It is recommended that the Director of the International Relations Office lead the change management process by promoting system adoption, monitoring system performance, and providing policy guidelines for system use, particularly in ensuring that data privacy and confidentiality standards are upheld.
4. Applicants are encouraged to utilize the system to submit their applications, monitor their status in real time, and stay informed through the system's notification features. This promotes a more transparent, efficient, and user-friendly application experience.
5. The researchers are encouraged to continue monitoring the system's performance, gather user feedback, and apply iterative improvements as needed. They should also document any challenges or successes encountered during the initial implementation to serve as a reference for future system development.
6. Future researchers are encouraged to explore the integration of additional features, such as automated document verification, online payment gateways, or AI-powered recommendation systems. They are also advised to consider conducting comparative studies with other universities offering ETEEAP to benchmark best practices and further improve the system's capabilities.

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